

COMMON PROBLEMS FACED BY FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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Xorazm viloyati Urganch tumani 6-son maktabning ingliz tili fani o`qituvchisi

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Annotation. Learning foreign language as a second language is not really easy. If you are learning language outside of the country which learning language is spoken, certainly you encounter certain kind of problems. These problems can make some obstacles to grasp new language although the learner are willing to learn new language.

Key words: Problem, solve, issue, learning process, obstacle, learner, key, instructor, learning environment, study, native language, dependence, dominate, solution, second language, learning materials.

Obstacles can be encountered by learners in every day life without any hesitating we can say. These are extremely different but the main ones can be said that we may count with our fingers. Language disorders that are often referred to as speech disorders interfere with an individual's ability to speak. There are numerous disorders and each has its own distinct symptoms. According to Whitaker language problems among students can be grouped into several categories that are related communication. For instance, there are problems associated with hearing, speech, language development and fluency. Whilst, the most common disorder is the speech impairment that involves articulation and voice. In this case, articulation involves numerous aspects of speech such as sounds, phonology and syllables. In most cases, students who develop such disorder in their childhood stage may experience the condition persisting to adulthood. Different students can have different difficulties and problems in learning a foreign language as a second language. Such as while learning English language most learners often face the following challenges:

Limited learning environments. It is not about the weather, the availability of furniture in the classrooms, the location of the building where new language is learning. Despite of the fact that all of the factors can effect learning while learning English, what happens outside of class matters most. In most situations, learners only make an effort to speak proper English in the classroom when they are under supervision. In addition to this, students do not always hear people around them speaking proper English. Unqualified teachers. This is the most vital and the most overlooked problem among others. What makes this problem so hard to solve is that , because many communities are English language learners, they can not clarify who is a good teacher and who is not. Whatever the teacher says, whether correct or incorrect, will be taken as correct by the learner. It can be led to great deal of confusion among learners since different teachers say them different things. Surplus usage of native language in the classroom. Each student can learn another language best when they are forced to apply it. Instructors must be vigilant about requiring students to communicate in English and only in English even if they are talking to each other. They must conduct the lesson with the help of direct method and the lesson will be effectively as well as reasonable. If the teachers know the student's language, it is better to pretend in the classroom that they do not, as that will force them to make requests and respond to questions in English. This issue may come from the cultural demands of the family and society.

Strong students dominate during the lesson. No matter how the learners are divided into groups, there will still be differences in how much students know and quickly they can learn. The most important problem of this situation is setting the pace of the class to keep up with the strongest learners. It may leave the weaker ones behind. Weaker ones should not be forgotten in classroom discussions and activities. But also they should be the main scenes of the lesson. They insist much more attention than others.

All things considered, each learner has his or her own issues but the most common that are mentioned above even though different instructors can give

different information about their student’s problems during learning language. These problems may be like these ones:

-lack of vocabulary; -correct pronunciation;

-hesitation in speaking; -understanding the grammar the structure of the new language;

-lack of interest;

-most of the students use the translation method to understand the second language.

The most common cause of the problems faced by a learner of the English language as a second language is existence of the inherent structure of their first language or mother tongue that they are exposed to since the first day. The above mentioned problems are just a few of other problems but these are the major ones faced by students. The hardest for a teacher in this case is to actually create a new structure of the English grammar while trying not to dismantle the existing language structure of their mother tongue. The student should be able to use the languages with ease. Even with qualified teachers, adequate materials, and exposure to native English speakers, there are still a number of problems that any ESL student will face. For the learners who are willing to grasp the foreign knowledge, there are number of steps they can take to improve their English language skills. To illustrate, they must be extra careful to be sure to use correct materials recommended by a reliable teacher of English and they should get audio materials so he or she can hear the clear and correct pronunciation of the strange words.

References:

1. Jacobs A. A “Challenges encountered by learners of English language” (2019)
2. Geri McClymont “Simple strategies to help English language learners succeed in the classroom” (2020)
3. Jeff Davis “Teaching ESL: Common problems in the classroom” (2016)
4. Jake Brannen “Why learn a foreign language? The importance of multilingualism and international awareness” (2014)